

PREDICTION OF LOW-ORDER ORIENTATION STATISTICS FOR ALIGNMENT OF LIQUID CRYSTALLINE POLYMERS IN HOMOGENEOUS SHEAR

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SUMMARY: A new closure approximation for the orientation tetradic is used to predict the equilibrium and non-equilibrium microstructure for liquid crystalline polymers subjected to rotary Brownian motion and a self-alignment process. In the absence of deformation, the isotropic equilibrium state is stable provided the dimensionless nematic strength U is below a critical value $U_c \cong 4$. For $U > U_c$, the theory predicts a trifurcation of equilibrium states with the simultaneous existence of an unstable three-dimensional isotropic orientation, a stable prolate orientation, and a stable oblate orientation. In the presence of homogeneous shear flows, the orientation director shows periodic behavior relative to the fixed flow direction. For $U = 30$ and $Pe = 25$, a *tumbling microstructure* is predicted with a frequency $\omega \cong 3\pi D_R$, where D_R represents a rotary diffusion coefficient. For a larger value of the Peclet number ($Pe = 38$), a *wagging microstructure* with $\omega \cong 4\pi D_R$ is observed for $U = 30$. A flow-aligning *nematic microstructure* occurs for $U = 30$ and $Pe = 80$.

KEYWORDS: Liquid crystalline polymers, orientation statistics, closure approximation, equilibrium states, self-alignment, flow induced alignment, simple shear.

INTRODUCTION

The prediction of mixing statistics of multiphase materials during processing has practical implications inasmuch as the microstructure dramatically influences the mechanical and transport properties of composite materials and blends [1]. Thus, flow-induced alignment of the dispersed phase will have a significant impact on developing materials such as short fiber composites and liquid crystalline polymers.

Model predictions of low-order statistical properties characteristic of the microstructure are often based on a moment equation for the orientation dyadic $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}} (\equiv \langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle)$, where the instantaneous orientation vector \mathbf{p} represents the relative alignment of a constituent component of the dispersed phase. The solution to the moment equation for $\langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle$ requires knowledge of the local flow field as well as a closure model for the orientation tetradic $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$. Unfortunately, the widespread use of this approach for the microstructure has been limited by the absence of a practical and accurate closure model that relates the dispersed phase orientation tetradic (fourth-order moment) to the dispersed phase orientation dyadic (second-order moment). Ongoing research at MSU by Petty *et al.* [2] addresses this fundamental issue of multiphase mixing for a wide class of physical problems by using a new closure approximation that retains the six-fold symmetry and projection (contraction) properties of the exact orientation tetradic. Cintra and Tucker [3] and Dupret *et al.* [4] have developed an orthotropic representation of $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$ that also retains the symmetry and contraction properties of the exact orientation tetradic.

MICROSTRUCTURE THEORY

The velocity gradient for simple homogeneous shear has a single component given by $\nabla \mathbf{u} = \dot{\gamma} \mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_3$ with $\dot{\gamma} = \text{constant}$. For this flow field, the microstructure is determined by the following evolution equation for the second moment of the orientation distribution function [5,6]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathbf{a}}{d\tau} = & \text{Pe} [\mathbf{e}_3 \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_3 - 2\mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_3 : \langle \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} \rangle] \\ & - \left(\mathbf{a} - \frac{1}{3} \mathbf{I} \right) + U \left(\mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a} : \langle \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}\mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} \rangle \right) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The foregoing Doi theory of liquid crystalline polymers seeks a balance between the flow alignment process and the rotary diffusion process in orientation space. U is a dimensionless measure of the strength of the Maier-Saupe potential and accounts for the excluded volume self-alignment effect on the rotary diffusive flux. The dimensionless time τ equals $6D_{Rt}$, where D_R represents a rotary diffusion coefficient in orientation space and t is the independent variable time. The Peclet number is defined by $\text{Pe} \equiv \dot{\gamma}/(6D_R)$. The above model for the microstructure assumes that the aspect ratio of the dispersed phase is large compared to unity.

The eigenvalues λ_i associated with the orientation dyadic $\langle \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} \rangle$ are positive. Each eigenvalue must satisfy the inequality $0 \leq \lambda_i \leq 1$ inasmuch as $\text{tr}(\langle \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} \rangle) = 1$. This realizability constraint on $\langle \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} \rangle$ also implies that the eigenvalues of the anisotropic structure tensor, which is defined by

$$\mathbf{b} \equiv \mathbf{a} - \frac{1}{3} \mathbf{I}, \quad (2)$$

are bounded and that $I_b \equiv \text{tr}(\mathbf{b}) = 0$. Figure 1 shows the realizable set of anisotropic orientation states associated with the other two invariants of the anisotropic structure tensor [2]:

$$II_b \equiv \text{tr}(\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{b}) \quad (3)$$

$$III_b \equiv \text{tr}(\mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{b} \cdot \mathbf{b}). \quad (4)$$

Point A (i.e., $II_b = 2/3$ and $III_b = 2/9$) on Figure 1 gives the invariants for a structure tensor corresponding to a *nematic orientation state* (i.e., $\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{e}_3 \mathbf{e}_3$). Point C ($II_b = 1/6$ and $III_b = -1/36$) corresponds to a *planar isotropic state* ($2\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_2 + \mathbf{e}_3 \mathbf{e}_3$); and, Point E ($II_b = 0$ and $III_b = 0$) corresponds to a *three-dimensional isotropic state* ($3\mathbf{a} = \mathbf{e}_1 \mathbf{e}_1 + \mathbf{e}_2 \mathbf{e}_2 + \mathbf{e}_3 \mathbf{e}_3$).

On the two-dimensional anisotropic boundary line B of Figure 1, the eigenvalues of $\langle \mathbf{p}\mathbf{p} \rangle$ are $[0, 1-\lambda_3, \lambda_3]$ with $1/2 \leq \lambda_3 \leq 1$; on the prolate axisymmetric boundary line F, the eigenvalues are $[(1-\lambda_3)/2, (1-\lambda_3)/2, \lambda_3]$ with $1/3 \leq \lambda_3 \leq 1$; and, on the oblate axisymmetric boundary D, the eigenvalues are given by $[1-2\lambda_3, \lambda_3, \lambda_3]$ with $1/3 \leq \lambda_3 \leq 1/2$.

Brave *et al.*[7] use the following scalar parameter to define the degree of orientation order:

$$S \equiv +\left(\frac{3}{2} \Pi_b\right)^{1/2} \quad \text{for } \Pi_b \geq 0; \text{ and,} \quad (5a)$$

$$S \equiv -\left(\frac{3}{2} \Pi_b\right)^{1/2} \quad \text{for } \Pi_b \leq 0. \quad (5b)$$

A perfectly aligned state (or nematic state) corresponds to $S = 1$ (Point A on Figure1). A planar isotropic state (Point C on Figure 1) corresponds to $S = -1/2$. A three-dimensional isotropic state (Point E on Figure 1) corresponds to $S = 0$.

The *director* \mathbf{n} of the microstructure is the eigenvector associated with the largest eigenvalue of the orientation dyadic $\langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle$. For homogeneous shear flows, the microstructure tends to align with the flow direction. An instantaneous measure of the relative alignment of the orientation director and the flow direction is given by

$$\mathbf{n} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\|\mathbf{u}\|} \equiv \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 = n_3 = \cos(\chi) , \quad (6)$$

where χ is the angle between the two unit vectors \mathbf{n} and \mathbf{e}_3 .

CLOSURE APPROXIMATION

A *fully symmetric quadratic* (FSQ-) closure for the fourth order moment of the orientation distribution is given by [2]:

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle = (1 - C_2) \langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_1 + C_2 \langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_2. \quad (7)$$

In the above equation, the fourth order moment $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_1$ is linear in $\langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle$ and was used earlier by Hand [7] as an approximation for the orientation tetradic near the isotropic state (Point E on Figure 1). $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_2$ is quadratic in $\langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle$ and was recently developed by Petty *et al.*[2]. A significant property of the FSQ-closure is that it explicitly satisfies all six-fold symmetry and projection properties of the exact orientation tetradic. The dimensionless coefficient C_2 depends on the invariants of $\langle \mathbf{pp} \rangle$ or, alternatively, the two nontrivial invariants of the anisotropic structure tensor defined by Eqs.(3) and (4) above.

The first-order and second-order tetradic components in the above representation are given by [2]

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_1 = -\frac{1}{35} S[\underline{\mathbf{I}} \underline{\mathbf{I}}] + \frac{1}{7} S[\underline{\mathbf{I}} \underline{\mathbf{a}}] \quad (8)$$

$$\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle_2 = +\frac{2}{35} (\underline{\mathbf{a}} : \underline{\mathbf{a}}) S[\underline{\mathbf{I}} \underline{\mathbf{I}}] + S[\underline{\mathbf{a}} \underline{\mathbf{a}}] - \frac{2}{7} S[\underline{\mathbf{I}} (\underline{\mathbf{a}} \cdot \underline{\mathbf{a}})]. \quad (9)$$

For symmetric operators $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}$ and $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}$, the components of the fully symmetric tetradic operators in the above representation are defined by

$$S[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}] \equiv A_{ij}A_{kl} + A_{ik}A_{jl} + A_{il}A_{kj} \quad (10)$$

$$S[\underline{\underline{\mathbf{A}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{B}}}] \equiv A_{ij}B_{kl} + A_{ik}B_{jl} + A_{il}B_{kj} + B_{ij}A_{kl} + B_{ik}A_{jl} + B_{il}A_{kj}. \quad (11)$$

The Doi theory [5] for liquid crystalline polymers uses the following *ad hoc*, albeit algebraically convenient, quadratic closure approximation for the dispersed phase orientation tetradic:

$$\langle \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}} \rangle_{QA} = \langle \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}} \rangle \langle \underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{P}}} \rangle \equiv \underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}. \quad (12)$$

Unlike Eq. (7) above, the *quadratic approximation* does not satisfy the six-fold symmetry and projection properties of the exact orientation tetradic operator.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Rotary Brownian Motion

For $Pe = 0$ and $U = 0$, the relaxation of the anisotropic structure tensor is governed by rotary Brownian motion and Eq.(1) reduces to the following differential equation

$$\frac{d\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}}}{d\tau} = -\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}}. \quad (13)$$

An analysis of this limiting case does not depend on a closure approximation for the orientation tetradic. Eq.(13) shows that any initial realizable anisotropic orientation state relaxes exponentially to an isotropic orientation state inasmuch as

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}} = \underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}}_0 \exp(-\tau) \rightarrow \underline{\underline{\mathbf{O}}}. \quad (14)$$

Clearly, if $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}}_0$ has a diagonal structure, then so does $\underline{\underline{\mathbf{b}}}(\tau)$. Eq.(14) also implies that the instantaneous values of $\Pi_b(\tau)$ and $\text{III}_b(\tau)$ for rotary Brownian motion are related by

$$\text{III}_b(\tau) / \text{III}_b(0) = [\Pi_b(\tau) / \Pi_b(0)]^{3/2} = [\exp(-2\tau)]^{3/2} = \exp(-3\tau). \quad (15)$$

Realizability

The above modification of the Doi theory is used to predict the transient and steady state microstructure of a dispersed phase for $Pe \geq 0$ and $U > 0$. Eq.(1) was integrated numerically using a second-order Runge-Kutta algorithm subject to the following class of initial conditions with a temporal step size $\Delta\tau = 0.003$ for all calculations:

$$\underline{\underline{\mathbf{a}}}_0 = a_{11}(0)\mathbf{e}_1\mathbf{e}_1 + a_{22}(0)\mathbf{e}_2\mathbf{e}_2 + a_{33}(0)\mathbf{e}_3\mathbf{e}_3. \quad (16)$$

The orientation states at $\tau = 0$ were selected from the boundary of Figure 1. For this study, all the initial states are nematic (i.e. $\mathbf{n}(0) \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 = 1$) and satisfy the following two conditions:

- $a_{11}(0) + a_{22}(0) + a_{33}(0) = 1.$
- $0 \leq a_{11}(0) \leq a_{22}(0) \leq a_{33}(0).$

Under these initial conditions, Eq.(1) yields realizable orientation states under the FSQ-closure with $C_2 = 1/3$ for $0 \leq Pe \leq 80$ and $0 \leq U \leq 30$. The above class of initial states may also be sufficient for realizabilty for larger values of Pe and U , but this has not been verified yet.

Equilibrium States

For $Pe = 0$ and $U > U_c$, the equilibrium states are not isotropic [5,6]. For this situation, the low order statistical properties of the microstructure depend on the closure approximation for the orientation tetradic $\langle \mathbf{pppp} \rangle$. Figure 2 compares the equilibrium states (i.e., $Pe = 0$) predicted by the FSQ-closure with those predicted by the quadratic closure [5] for $0 \leq U \leq 10$. All the equilibrium states occur on the boundary of the realizability region of Figure 1. The parameter S , defined by Eq.(5), is used to characterize the degree of orientation of the equilibrium states.

Both closures show a trifurcation of equilibrium states above a critical value of U . For $U < U_c \cong 2.7$, the quadratic-closure predicts that the isotropic state is stable to finite disturbances. On the other hand, the FSQ-closure yields stable isotropic states for $U < U_c \cong 4$. The two closures show significant qualitative differences in the transition to multiple equilibrium states. For example, the quadratic model anticipates a range of unstable prolate states ($S > 0$) for $2.7 < U < 3$, but the FSQ-closure does not show this subcritical trifurcation phenomena. Furthermore, the FSQ-closure predicts that the oblate states ($S < 0$) are stable to finite oblate disturbances. On the other hand, Brave *et al.* [6] indicate that the oblate state is unstable if the quadratic approximation, defined by Eq.(12), is used as a closure for Eq.(1).

Figure 3 shows the position on the realizability diagram of the multiple equilibrium states predicted by the FSQ-closure for $U > U_c$. A FSQ-prolate equilibrium state attracts all initial states on the boundary B and the Boundary F (see Figure 1). The complementary FSQ-oblate state attracts all initial states on the Boundary D. Although the isotropic state is a steady state solution to Eq.(1) with a FSQ-closure, this state is unstable to any infinitesimal disturbance for $U > U_c \cong 4$.

Periodic States

The FSQ-closure predicts a *tumbling microstructure* for $U = 30$ and $Pe = 25$. Figure 4 shows the transient behavior of the orientation director projected onto the flow axis (see Eq. (6) above). The transition to a periodic state from the initial nematic state (Point A on Figure 1) occurs in about one half cycle. Although the orientation director rotates completely around the fixed flow direction, $\mathbf{n}(\tau)$ remains approximately aligned with the flow direction for most of the cycle before tumbling rapidly through 360° . The overall cycle is repeated with a frequency $\omega \cong 3\pi D_R$. The actual tumbling event occurs rapidly over a time scale comparable to $T/10$, where $T = 2\pi/\omega$.

For $Pe = 37$ and $U = 30$, the FSQ-closure predicts a *wagging microstructure*. Figure 5 shows that the microstructure changes from its initial nematic state with $a_{33} = 1$ (Point A on Figure 1) to a periodic state within one half cycle. As indicated by Figure 5, the orientation director remains approximately aligned with the fixed flow direction for most of the cycle before executing a wagging motion. The frequency for the wagging event is approximately $4\pi D_R$. It is noteworthy that the wagging episode occurs over a time scale comparable to $T/5$, where $T = 2\pi/\omega$.

For $Pe = 80$ and $U = 30$, Eq.(1) together with the FSQ-closure predicts a *jittering microstructure* with the director slightly wagging about the fixed flow direction with a frequency $\omega \cong 24\pi D_R$, which is much higher than predicted for the *tumbling microstructure* of the *wagging microstructure*. The significant finding reported herein is the discovery that the fully symmetric quadratic model with $C_2 = 1/3$ predicts a transition from a *tumbling microstructure* to a *jittering* (\cong *steady*) *microstructure* as the Peclet number increases for a fixed nematic strength.

As noted by Brave *et al.* [6], the quadratic approximation does not predict the periodic states anticipated by exact solutions to the underlying equation governing the orientation distribution function. Furthermore, Chaubal and Leal [8] have shown that a closure approximation based on the Bingham distribution, albeit realizable, does not predict a flow-aligning transition in simple shear. However, the FSQ-closure of the orientation tetradic, disclosed by Petty *et al.* at ICCM 12 [2], provides a realizable closure to the moment equation governing the orientation dyadic for liquid crystalline polymers. The new closure predicts multiple equilibrium states for $Pe = 0$; periodic states for $Pe > 0$; and a transition to a self-aligning regime for large values of the Peclet number.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was funded by the National Science Foundation (CTS-9986878) and the Composite Materials and Structures Center at Michigan State University. The authors are grateful for this support.

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Figure 1. Realizable Set of Anisotropic Orientation States

Figure 2. Comparison of Equilibrium States Predicted by the FSQ-Closure (lower graph, this research) and Quadratic Closure (upper graph, Brave *et al.* [6]) for $Pe = 0$ and $0 \leq U \leq 10$

Figure 3. Location of Multiple FSQ-Equilibrium States on the Realizable Diagram for $4.5 \leq U \leq 6$

Figure 4. Tumbling Microstructure. Relative alignment of the orientation director with the flow direction predicted by the FSQ-Closure for $U = 30$, $Pe = 25$

Figure 5. Wagging Microstructure. Relative alignment of the orientation director with the flow direction predicted by the FSQ-Closure for $U = 30$, $Pe = 38$